

Supplemental Figure S1. Examples of calves rubbing their paste, which can appear orange or black in color, either down their face (A), or on their hutch (B, C, D).

Supplemental Figure S2. Examples of calves with large paste wounds on their horn buds, and secondary burns on their ears and side of the head.

Supplemental Figure S3. Examples of calves with dried paste either near their eye (A) or damage from paste in the eye (B).

Supplemental Figure S4. Examples of calves with large, “dinner plate” like wounds, creating more damage than is necessary to prevent horn growth.

Supplemental Figure S6. Examples of calves paste rubbed on their legs (A & B), and a secondary burn on the leg from paste (C).

Supplemental Figure S7. A calf with caustic paste rubbed on her head and face after application for disbudding. If left in contact with the head, secondary burns will occur anywhere the paste is contacting. Paste can be removed and neutralized with vinegar. If removed promptly, secondary burns will not occur.

Supplemental Figure S8. A calf with caustic paste burn running down the side of her face, paste on her ear, and rubbed on the hutch.

Supplemental Figure S9. Large secondary burns from hot-iron disbudding when the horn bud was removed/“scooped out”.

Supplemental Figure S10. Mechanical nociceptive threshold measures (MNT) for caustic paste disbudded calves who received 0.2 or 0.3 mL per shaved horn bud. Model predicted means \pm SE over time are shown for horn buds where calves did (1) or did not (0) rub the paste onto their pen or other body part on the day of disbudding. We found evidence of an interaction between rubbing, dose, and observation day ($P < 0.01$) such that 0.3 mL horn buds that were not rubbed became more sensitive over time and 0.2 unrubbed buds became less sensitive.

Supplemental Figure S11. Examples of detaching necrotic tissue after caustic paste disbudded showing a ring of hair between the burned area of application and the total area of necrotic tissue.